

Statistical Considerations of the Dirac Type 2x2 Linear Matrix Equation

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In a number of notes, a 2x2 Dirac type matrix equation, linear in energy, was written to describe Einstein's 1905 energy-momentum equation $E^2=p^2 + m^2$ (1). The 2-vector positive energy eigenvector $1/\sqrt{2} (\sqrt{1+v}, \sqrt{1-v})$ with $c=1$ was found as a solution. It suggests probabilities of $(1+v)/2$ and $(1-v)/2$ for the particle bouncing back and forth along the x direction in a box moving with speed v in the x direction. It can also be thought of as a bouncing photon in the rest frame. In the lab frame, the photon would have a Doppler shifted energy $(m/2) \sqrt{1+v}/\sqrt{1-v}$ moving forward and $(m/2) \sqrt{1+v}/\sqrt{1-v}$ moving backward. These added give a total energy of $m/\sqrt{1-v^2}$ and a momentum of $mv/\sqrt{1-v^2}$. Knuth (18) has also developed a model suggesting that there are probabilities of $(1+v)/2$ and $(1-v)/2$ for particle motion backward and forward as the particle moves forward on average with speed v . In the 2x2 matrix model developed in [2]-[9], it was shown that this bouncing motion was also associated with zitterbewegung and the results of the Dirac equation zitterbewegung [1] were obtained.

It is possible to obtain the probabilities $(1+v)/2$ and $(1-v)/2$ readily using $P_1+P_2=1$ and $P_1-P_2=v$. It is, however, also possible to obtain these probabilities by finding a stationary solution of entropy: $f_1 \ln(f_1) + f_2 \ln(f_2) + w(f_1-f_2)$, where a constraint associated with $f_1-f_2=v$ has been implemented. This leads to solutions of $\exp(w)$ and $\exp(-w)$ where $\exp(w)=\sqrt{1+v}/\sqrt{1-v}$ i.e. the Doppler result for an approaching photon and $\exp(-w)$ the Doppler frequency for a photon moving away from the viewer.

Relativistic Statistical Mechanical Model of Kaniadakis

Recently, a new approach to relativistic statistical mechanics has been developed by Kaniadakis [19] who took the two equations which exist in the literature related to relativistic kinematics:

$$G(1/f)=-G(f)$$

$$d/df [f(G(f))] = (1/g) G(vf)$$

Where $G = d/df$ (entropy density) and g and v need to be determined. We do not go into any details of his theory here, but refer the reader to [19].

Kaniadakis showed that there are two solutions. The first uses $g=1$ $v=e$ (the exponential) and yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution with the relativistic energy being used. A second solution, however, is given by:

$$G(f) = (1/2k) [f^{(1-k)}/(1-k) - f^{(1+k)}/(1+k)]$$

Where $1/k^2$ is the rest mass and in the nonrelativistic limit $k \rightarrow 0$, the natural logarithm is recovered. (Ultimately, his theory gives a distribution other than the Maxwell-Boltzmann. His does not die off as quickly and apparently describes relativistic data which is now available.)

$$g = 1/\sqrt{1-k^2}$$

$$\text{And } v = (\sqrt{1+k^2g^2} + kg)^{1/k}$$

He then proposes an entropy given by $(1/2k) \int d^3p f^{(1-k)}/(1-k) - f^{(1+k)}/(1+k)$

Kaniadakis also finds an explicit form for f , the distribution in terms of $(1/T)(E-\mu)$ where T is the temperature, E the relativistic particle energy and μ the chemical potential. [19]

Interestingly, $\exp(w)$ and $\exp(-w)$ from the 2×2 matrix model are stationary solutions of Kaniadakis' approach, if one uses $d/df S(\text{Kaniadakis}) + d/df w(f_1-f_2)$ to obtain an equation for f_1 and another for f_2 . Here $w(f_1-f_2)$ is associated with the constraint $f_1-f_2 = v$

Thus, $(1+v)/2$ and $(1-v)/2$ would be stationary solutions of either model of relativistic statistical mechanics, that of Kaniadakis and the regular which uses $-\ln(f)$ for the entropy term. It should be noted that $(1+v)/2$ and $(1-v)/2$ arise from the 2×2 matrix formalism of the relativistic energy-momentum equation (1) and so should apply to the relativistic case. In the nonrelativistic case, one has a Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution for energies which matches nonrelativistic experimental data. Apparently somewhat recent data shows that the MB distribution does not match data in the tail for relativistic cosmic rays at relativistic energies. Thus, it seems that one might want a different distribution for the relativistic case which in the nonrelativistic limit becomes the MB distribution.

It would be interesting if the result of $\exp(w)$ and $\exp(-w)$ could anticipate the results of Kaniadakis [19]. We note that there would be a function representing entropy which can be written as $f G(f)$ where G is arbitrary and f is the distribution. Then, one can vary with respect to the function f_1 and then f_2

$$[f_1 G(f_1)] + [f_2 G(f_2)] + w(f_1-f_2)$$

And set it equal to zero. One finds that $D[f_1 G(f_1)] = -w$ and $D[f_2 G(f_2)] = w$. With $f_1 = 1/f_2$.

In addition, $fG(f)$ should become $\ln(f)$ in the nonrelativistic limit.

A function of the form $(f^k - f^k)^{n+1}$ would give the $-w / +w$ behaviour, but the $n+1$ exponent may cause trouble with a limit going to a \ln , so one can consider $(f^k - f^k)$ which would result from an entropy of $[f^{(1-k)}/(1-k) - f^{(1+k)}/(1+k)]$. Multiplying by a factor of $1/2k$ would give the limiting \ln behaviour as $k \rightarrow 0$.

Now: $\ln(x) = \lim_{a \rightarrow 0} [x^{(-a)} - x^{(a)}] / 2a$ and $[x^{(-a)} - x^{(a)}] / 2a$ is exactly the term Kaniadakis [19] uses for his generalized log function.

$$S = 1/2k \int d^3p [f^{(1-k)} / (1-k) - f^{(1+k)} / (1+k)]$$

So it seems that one could “guess” Kaniadakis’ solution for the entropy from the 2x2 matrix model. This does not guarantee that it is the most general solution, but it does yield the probabilities of the 2x2 matrix model $(1+v)/2$ and $(1-v)/2$ and becomes the MB distribution in the nonrelativistic limit.

Effect of Bouncing Photon on Distribution

The 2x2 matrix model considered in terms of probability may contribute a factor to the overall calculation of distributions. In the case of a photon bouncing back and forth along the x axis in a box moving with speed v in the x direction, one has the entropy:

$$-k \cdot 5 [(1+v)\ln(1+v) + (1-v)\ln(1-v)] = k \ln(\# \text{ of states}) \quad \text{where } k \text{ is the Boltzmann constant}$$

$$\# \text{ of states} = [1/\sqrt{1-v^2}] [\sqrt{1-v}/\sqrt{1+v}]^v$$

In the non-relativistic limit of $v \rightarrow 0$ one obtains # of states = 1 while in the ultra-relativistic limit of $v \rightarrow 1$ one obtains $1/2$. Here v is really v/c .

The number of states in this case is a function of v and so could affect the velocity distribution at a given temperature. Thus, one might write for the probability of having a Dirac-like particle with an energy E at a temperature T.

$$d^3p [[1/\sqrt{1-v^2}] \{ \sqrt{1-v}/\sqrt{1+v} \}^v \{ \sqrt{1+k^2x^2} + kx \}^{1/k}$$

Where $1/k^2$ is the rest mass and $x=(E-\mu)/T$ where T is temperature, μ the chemical potential and E the energy of the particle.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the 2x2 Dirac-like matrix linearization of the energy-momentum equation (1) can be interpreted as a probability scenario. It was argued in [2] that this was in fact a quantum mechanical probabilistic approach as it leads to the Schrodinger zitterbewegung [1]. We have also seen that the probabilities $.5(1+v)$ and $.5(1-v)$ associated with the energy eigenvector $.5(\sqrt{1+v}, \sqrt{1-v})$ can also be obtained by finding a stationary solution of the entropy given by $-k f_1 \ln(f_1) - k f_2 \ln(f_2) - w (f_1 - f_2)$ where the constraint $f_1 - f_2 = v$ has been used. The unnormalized

results are $f_1 = \sqrt{(1+v)/1-v}$ and $f_2 = 1/f_1$, i.e. the two Doppler shift scenarios. Kaniadakis [19] has developed a relativistic statistical model in which the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution only holds in the nonrelativistic case. He instead uses for entropy:

$$S = \frac{1}{2k} \int d^3p \left[\frac{f^{(1-k)}}{(1-k)} - \frac{f^{(1+k)}}{(1+k)} \right]$$

One can see that f_1 and $f_2 = 1/f_1$ together with the constraint $f_1 - f_2 = v$ are also stationary solutions of this new relativistic entropy. In fact, we suggest that one could use the f_1 and $f_2 = 1/f_1$ result to postulate Kaniadakis entropy expression such that it becomes the natural logarithm in the $k \rightarrow 0$ (nonrelativistic) limit. Kaniadakis' new expression for the natural logarithm is the sum of the mathematical limits $-\ln(a) = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} [a^{-x} - 1]/x$ and $\ln(a) = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} [a^x - 1]/x$. f_1 and f_2 from the 2×2 matrix model should already be relativistic expressions and so are not "nonrelativistic limits". It turns out they provide stationary solutions to both Kaniadakis' relativistic entropy expression and the normal $S = -k \int f \ln(f)$ expression which leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann result. The experimental motivation for a new relativistic distribution is that relativistic data apparently does not match the tail the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

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